

Electrochemical and electron paramagnetic resonance studies of some oxovanadium(IV) complexes with ONO donor Schiff base ligands

Jagdish Prasad*, Prem Yadav, Ved Prakash and Krishna Srivastava

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : dr_jagdish_p@yahoo.co.in; dr_krishna_s@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 10 August 2005, revised 18 May 2007, accepted 21 May 2007

Abstract : The electrochemical and EPR spectral properties of some oxovanadium(IV) complexes with Schiff bases (Sal-AA) derived from salicylaldehyde and six aminoacids, viz. glycine, L-alanine, L-phenylalanine, DL-valine, L-leucine and L-methionine have been studied at a Pt working electrode in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), dimethylformamide (DMF) and 50% DMSO-aqueous (v/v) media containing 0.1 M tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP) as supporting electrolyte by means of cyclic voltammetry. In DMSO/0.1 M TBAP, all these [VO(Sal-AA)H₂O] complexes exhibited a totally irreversible anodic peak at +590 ± 10 mV vs SCE at a scan rate 25 mV/s while in 50% DMSO-aqueous (v/v)/0.1 M TBAP media, a quasi-reversible VO²⁺/VO³⁺ couple with a formal potential, E^{0'} = +390 mV vs SCE was observed. The X-band EPR spectra of these complexes in DMSO at 300 and 77 K were also recorded and their salient features are reported.

Keywords : Cyclic voltammetry, electrochemistry, vanadyl compounds, Schiff base complexes, electron paramagnetic resonance spectroscopy.

Schiff bases, their derivatives and their metal complexes have been found to have potential application in industry and biology¹. The derivatives of such compounds as such and also after suitable structural modifications may become potential candidates for industry. Coordination chemistry of vanadium has attracted interest during the last few years, due to the model character of many vanadium complexes for the biological function of vanadium¹⁻⁵. The active site structures of the vanadate dependent haloperoxidases have been revealed by X-ray diffraction studies. Accordingly the vanadate ion is distorted towards a trigonal bipyramid, providing a fifth coordination site which is occupied by N of a histidine, covalently linking the vanadate ion to the protein⁶. These enzymes lose their activity on reduction or removal of vanadium; re-oxidation or re-constitution with vanadate fully restores their activity indicating that V^V (VO³⁺ or VO₂⁺) is essential for catalytic activity.

Keeping in view the above points we have investigated the electrochemical and EPR spectral properties of some oxovanadium(IV) complexes with Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde and various amino acids such as glycine, NH₂CH₂COOH; L-alanine, CH₃CH(NH₂)COOH; L-phenylalanine, C₆H₅CH₂CH(NH₂)COOH; DL-valine, (CH₃)₂CH.CH(NH₂)COOH; L-leucine, (CH₃)₂CHCH₂CH(NH₂)COOH and L-methionine, CH₃S(CH₂)₂CH(NH₂)COOH. The ligands are abbrevi-

ated as (Sal-AA) and they act as bivalent anions with tridentate ONO donor atoms.

Results and discussion

The electrochemical behaviour of 4 mM oxovanadium(IV) complexes, [VO(Sal-AA)H₂O] with Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde and six amino acids have been investigated at a Pt-electrode in DMSO, DMF and 50% DMSO-aqueous media (v/v) containing 0.1 M TBAP. The complexes have the following square pyramidal geometrical arrangement⁷ :

All these oxovanadium(IV)-Schiff base complexes exhibited almost similar CV behaviour in DMSO and DMF containing 0.1 M TBAP. The cyclic voltammograms showed a totally irreversible oxidation peak at E_{pa} = +590 ± 10 mV in the forward positive scan initiated at 0.0 V and one reduction peak at E_{pc} = -130 ± 10 mV in the reverse cycle in the potential range from +0.85 to -0.80 V vs SCE. The associated peaks corresponding to

Table 1. Cyclic voltammetric parameters for 4 mM [VO(Sal-AA)H₂O] Schiff base complexes in DMSO containing 0.1 M TBAP

Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	E_{pa} (mV)	E_{pc} (mV)	I_{pa} (μ A)	I_{pc} (μ A)
[VO(Sal-glycine)H₂O]				
25	+600	-120	3.2	0.2
50	+600	-125	4.6	0.3
100	+620	-130	6.2	0.4
200	+630	-140	9.3	0.5
300	+650	-150	11.0	0.6
400	+680	-160	12.8	0.7
[VO(Sal-L-alanine)H₂O]				
25	+600	-120	4.4	0.3
50	+610	-125	7.0	0.5
100	+630	-130	9.6	0.7
200	+650	-140	14.0	0.8
300	+670	-160	16.7	0.9
400	+670	-170	18.7	1.1
[VO(Sal-L-phenylalanine)H₂O]				
25	+600	-120	4.4	0.3
50	+620	-125	7.0	0.5
100	+640	-130	9.5	0.6
200	+650	-140	14.0	0.7
300	+670	-160	16.7	0.8
400	+670	-170	18.7	1.1
[VO(Sal-DL-valine)H₂O]				
25	+580	-140	4.6	0.4
50	+590	-150	6.6	0.5
100	+600	-150	9.0	0.6
200	+610	-160	12.9	0.7
300	+630	-170	15.2	0.8
400	+650	-170	17.5	0.9
[VO(Sal-L-leucine)H₂O]				
25	+590	-125	3.5	0.3
50	+590	-130	5.8	0.4
100	+600	-130	7.5	0.5
200	+630	-140	11.0	0.6
300	+650	-140	13.5	0.7
400	+665	-140	15.2	0.8
[VO(Sal-L-methionine)H₂O]				
25	+600	-130	5.0	0.4
50	+610	-140	7.0	0.6
100	+630	-150	9.5	0.7
200	+650	-155	13.5	0.8
300	+660	-160	16.0	0.9
400	+670	-170	18.0	1.0

these anodic and cathodic processes were not observed in the scan rate range studied, clearly indicating that the electrogenerated species are unstable and presumably the electron-transfer is followed by fast rearrangements of the products^{8,9}. It must be mentioned that 4 mM VOSO₄ in DMSO/or DMF solution containing 0.1 M TBAP does not yield any redox peak in the potential range studied, clearly indicating that the anodic peak ($E_{pa} \sim 590$ mV) is due to oxidation of a [VO(Sal-AA)H₂O] complex and not due to any other species like VO²⁺. A plot of I_{pa} vs $v^{1/2}$ gives a straight line passing through the origin, indicating that the electrode process is diffusion-controlled⁸. Controlled potential coulometry at +700 mV vs SCE indicates that this oxidation process involves one electron per molecule of the V^{IV}-Schiff base complex.

It may be noted that the anodic peak potentials are shifted positively by nearly 20 mV in DMF/0.1 M TBAP as compared to that in DMSO/0.1 M TBAP medium for all these complexes at a given scan rate (Tables 1 and 2). It must be noted that not only EPR spectral parameters are nearly identical (Table 4) but also the magnitudes of the anodic and cathodic peak potentials (E_{pa} and E_{pc}) for all these complexes are almost similar in a given medium at a given scan rate (Tables 1-3). This is due to the fact that these complexes have distorted square pyramidal geometry with identical donor environment involving 4 O and one N atom around the vanadium atom and also the donor and the crystal field strengths of Sal-AA Schiff base ligands are almost similar^{7,9}.

In 50% DMSO/0.1 M TBAP medium, the initial anodic scan initiated at +0.1 V in the potential range from +0.85 to -0.80 V vs SCE indicated an oxidation couple (VO²⁺/VO³⁺) in the positive potential region with formal potential $E^{\circ} = +390$ mV vs SCE and one totally irreversible cathodic peak at $E_{pc_2} = +110$ mV, at scan rate 25 mV s⁻¹ as shown in Fig. 1 (Table 3). A perusal of Table 3 shows that the anodic peak potential (E_{pa_1}) becomes less positive in 50% organo-aqueous medium (v/

Table 2. Cyclic voltammetric parameters for 4 mM [VO(Sal-glycine)H₂O] Schiff base complexes in DMF containing 0.1 M TBAP

Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	E_{pa} (mV)	E_{pc} (mV)	I_{pa} (μ A)	I_{pc} (μ A)
25	+630	+40	5.7	0.3
50	+640	+30	6.8	0.4
100	+660	+30	11.7	0.5
200	+670	+20	17.2	0.6
300	+680	+10	20.8	0.8
400	+710	0	23.7	1.0

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of 4 mM [VO(Sal-glycine)H₂O] in 50% DMSO-aqueous medium (v/v)/0.1 M TBAP at scan rate 25 mV s⁻¹.

v) as compared to that in organic-medium (Tables 1 and 2). The anodic-to-cathodic peak potential separation, ΔE_p ($E_{pa_1} - E_{pc_1}$) varies from 90 to 140 mV with increasing scan rate. Both these observations are indicative of the quasi-reversible one-electron transfer process^{8,9}. Constant potential coulometry at +550 mV vs SCE has confirmed the involvement of one electron per molecule of each of these complexes in 50% DMSO-aqueous medium containing 0.1 M TBAP. The parameter ΔE_p can be assumed as a rough index of the degree of departure from the electrochemical reversibility considering that for one electron charge transfer, ΔE_p is 60 mV. The plot of I_{pa_1} vs the square root of the scan rate ($v^{1/2}$) produced a straight line passing through origin, indicating that the electrode process is diffusion-controlled⁸. The ratio of cathodic peak current to the anodic peak current (I_{pc_1}/I_{pa_1}) is less than 1.0 (Table 3). This clearly shows that the VO³⁺-complex species are electrochemically unstable and undergo slow decomposition^{8,9}. The following reaction pathway may be suggested to explain the observed electrochemical data :

Table 3. Cyclic voltammetric parameters for 4 mM [VO(Sal-glycine)H₂O] in 50% DMSO-aqueous (v/v) medium containing 0.1 M TBAP

Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	E_{pa_1} (mV)	E_{pc_1} (mV)	$E_{pc_2}^a$ (mV)	I_{pa_1} (μA)	I_{pc} (μA)	$E^{o'}$ (mV)	ΔE_p (mV)	I_{pc_1}/I_{pa_1}
25	+430	+340	+110	5.0	3.4	+385	90	0.68
50	+435	+335	+100	7.2	4.9	+385	100	0.68
100	+445	+335	+80	10.2	7.0	+390	110	0.68
200	+445	+335	+60	14.5	10.0	+390	110	0.69
300	+450	+330	+50	17.2	11.8	+390	120	0.69
400	+460	+330	+40	20.0	14.0	+395	130	0.70
500	+470	+330	+30	22.0	15.4	+400	140	0.70

^a I_{pc_2} is not measurable.

EPR spectra : The [VO(Sal-AA)H₂O] complexes are EPR-active in DMSO solution at room temperature (RT = 300 K) and at liquid nitrogen temperature (LNT = 77 K). The EPR spectra of all these complexes are almost

Fig. 2. EPR spectra of $[\text{VO}(\text{Sal-glycine})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ at LNT (77 K) in frozen DMSO solution.

similar. The EPR parameters obtained from the spectra are listed in Table 4. The isotropic room temperature solution spectrum of 1 mM $[\text{VO}(\text{Sal-glycine})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ reveals the presence of eight-lines arranged in a more or less symmetrical manner (Fig. 2), showing coupling between the unpaired electron and ^{51}V ($I = 7/2$) nuclear spins. This clearly indicates that complexes in solution exist as monomer. In frozen solution, the EPR spectra of these complexes are anisotropic and show two types of resonance components, one set due to the parallel features and the other set due to the perpendicular features¹⁰. The observed resonance parameters $A_{\parallel} \gg A_{\perp}$ and $g_{\parallel} < g_{\perp}$ indicate that these complexes exist in a square-pyramidal geometry. No ligand super-hyperfine splittings are observed. This indicates that the unpaired electron is in an orbital which is localized on the metal, excluding any

possibility of its direct interaction with the incoming ligands¹¹.

Experimental

The $[\text{VO}(\text{Sal-AA})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ Schiff base complexes (AA = glycine, L-alanine, L-phenylalanine, DL-valine, L-leucine and L-methionine) were prepared according to methods described elsewhere⁷. The purity of these complexes was confirmed in each case by elemental analyses.

Cyclic voltammetry was carried out with a Bio-Analytical System (BAS) Model CV-1B (West Lafayette, Indiana, USA) instrument having an electrochemical cell with a three electrode system. The working electrode was a platinum microelectrode (MF 2013). The platinum wire was used as an auxiliary electrode, and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as a reference electrode, with $E^0 =$

Table 4. EPR parameters for [VO(Sal-AA)H₂O] Schiff base complexes in DMSO at 300 and 77 K

Complex	At 300 K		At 77 K					
	g_{iso}	A_{iso} (G)	$g_{ }$	g_{\perp}	$A_{ }$ (G)	A_{\perp} (G)	g_{av}	A_{av} (G)
[VO(Sal-glycine)H ₂ O]	1.976	50.8	1.950	1.987	180.1	65.4	1.975	103.6
[VO(Sal-L-alanine)H ₂ O]	1.972	51.3	1.951	1.985	183.2	66.2	1.974	105.2
[VO(Sal-L-phenylalanine)H ₂ O]	1.975	51.3	1.953	1.978	181.7	68.0	1.970	105.9
[VO(Sal-L-valine)H ₂ O]	1.970	51.3	1.952	1.985	182.4	66.1	1.974	104.9
[VO(Sal-L-leucine)H ₂ O]	1.976	51.4	1.955	1.988	180.8	65.4	1.977	103.9
[VO(Sal-L-methionine)H ₂ O]	1.974	51.6	1.956	1.987	184.4	66.8	1.976	106.0

$g_{av} = 1/3[2g_{\perp} + g_{||}]$; $A_{av} = 1/3[2A_{\perp} + A_{||}]$.

+0.242 V vs NHE. The cyclic voltammograms were recorded on an x-y recorder. All the cyclic voltammetry experiments were done in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen achieved by purging the cell solution with pure nitrogen gas for about 20 min. An inert atmosphere of nitrogen was also maintained over the cell solution during recording of the voltammograms. Tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP, 0.1 M) received from Fluka, was used as the supporting electrolyte. High purity dimethylsulfoxide and dimethylformamide were obtained from E. Merck. All experiments were performed at 30 ± 0.2 °C.

The EPR spectra were recorded on a Varian E-line Century series EPR spectrometer equipped with a dual cavity and operating at X-band with 100 KHz modulation. TCNE ($g = 2.00277$) was used as field marker. The EPR spectra of the complexes were recorded in DMSO solution at RT (300 K) and in frozen solution at LNT (77 K). The frozen samples were placed in a Varian liquid nitrogen Dewar flask for measurement at 77 K. The $g_{||}$ and $A_{||}$ values were measured according to the standard procedure¹².

Acknowledgement

We thank the RSIC, IIT Bombay for EPR facilities and Chemistry Department, BHU, Varanasi for coulometry measurements. We are also thankful to Prof. K. B. Pandeya and Prof. Rajeev Jain for valuable discussion.

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